

**AMBIVALENT DISCOURSE AND THE LANGUAGE OF MEDICAL PRACTICE:
EXAMINING THE NIGERIAN CONTEXT**

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Abstract

The purpose of this paper is to investigate aspects of medical discourse, with a view to interrogating their implicit ideologies which are ambivalent when considered in relation to the idea of saving life, which the profession seemingly professes. The concept, ambivalent discourse, has been borrowed from ecolinguistics. In ecolinguistics, it is believed that language choice in discourse intrinsically contains people's attitude and perception towards ecological co-existence. Thus, discourse becomes ambivalent when the choice of language implicates a promotion of what the discourse sets to discourage. The major argument of the paper is, therefore, that there are aspects of medical discourse which hide ambivalent ideologies that relegate patients to sub-human category. Such language choices tend to exonerate the medical personnel from any blame of incompetence in the event of any casualty, and they also end up reducing the dignity of the patients whom the medical doctors profess to be saving. The theoretical frame work that guides the analysis of the paper is social ecology theory, which identifies the root of ecological destruction as existing in the oppressive social hierarchies. The data for analysis in the paper were collected through personal observation, and the authors' interaction with patients, their relatives and the medical personnel. The method of analysis is qualitative, with particular attention to aspects of ambivalent discourse in the selected texts. The authors, therefore, join Bloor and Bloor to conclude that ideology can be so deeply ingrained in our thought patterns that we take them for granted. However, such hidden ideological position can be screened by closely examining the patterns of language use

Keywords: Language, Ideology, Ambivalent Discourse, Medical Practice
